

A New Construction Method of Carbon Fibre Hybrid GRP Moulds in Vacuum Forming Process

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ABSTRACT

This paper concerns use of hybrid GRP in constructing vacuum forming moulds for thermoplastics plates, resulting in higher efficiency, performance and other advantages.

The structural model has a sandwich construction, with hybrid GRP used as the surface material, and clearance provided between core blocks forming free air passage.

Vacuum suction pin holes are provided on the mould surface, for deaeration from one or more nozzles in the back for forming operation. A negative pressure is created in the double skin clearance while the atmospheric pressure in the front and rear surfaces of mould itself balances to maintain the shape accurately.

Now, constructing the double skin with CF hybrid GRP has provided the following advantages;

- a) Higher flexibility of mould construction
- b) Creep is prevented (in comparison with GRP double skin)
- c) Dimensional stability
- d) Improved efficiency of thermal conductivity allows to reduce cooling time to half by circulating cold air through the air passage between cores.

The weight of the mould, particularly, can be reduced to less than 1/5 to 1/10 of conventional GRP moulds or aluminum cast moulds. Other than the improved efficiency by reduction in weight, more than 30% save in time for changing moulds, with a proven contribution in remarkably reducing the mould cost.

INTRODUCTION

Large forms of thermoplastic sheet formed in vacuum are used in a wider range of application today. The mould material used in vacuum forming which is basically for mass production is cast aluminum, with some exception of GRP.

Moulds made of the conventional material have certain disadvantages, as listed below;

- a) The mould must be made thicker, and, consequently heavier, to withstand vacuum suction.
- b) The moulds are expanded by heat transfer from the heated thermoplastic sheet during forming, inevitably causing intolerable dimensional variations in products.
- c) Mould costs are high, and production is more time consuming.

If all these disadvantages could be removed by a new lightweight, accurate mould that could be prepared faster and less expensively, it would certainly be possible to improve productivity in manufacturing products of higher quality.

The writers have developed a new and original construction method of mould for vacuum forming using carbon fibre hybrid GRP, and this paper concerns such a new construction method.

OUTLINE OF THE MOULD CONSTRUCTION METHOD

The principle that underlies the mould construction is based on a patent held by KODAMA CHEMICAL INDUSTRY Co., Ltd.

Figure 1. is a sectional view of typical CF hybrid GRP mould, and Figure 2. shows a perspective section of its construction.

As shown in these illustrations, the mould has a sandwiched core construction, with the core pieces being arrayed with predetermined clearance between any two pieces except along the periphery. A uniqueness of this design is the air passage formed by these continuous clearance.

If a suction nozzle is provided in one or more of such air passages, and the mould is deaerated through such nozzles, a negative pressure will be caused in the voids in the cores. Therefore, vacuum suction pin holes are provided at appropriate positions in the surface skin above these clearance to use the mould in vacuum forming.

As shown, such a construction helps to maintain the original shape of the mould since atmospheric pressure act equally on both sides of the mould.

Figure 1. A model figure of CF hybrid mould section

Figure 2. Perspective model of mould construction

CF HYBRID GRP SURFACE SKIN AND CORE MATERIAL

1. CF hybrid Grp laminate construction and matrix resin

The writers compared several combinations of hybrid materials to use, and a matrix resin with high heatresistance was selected. Table 1. shows an example of laminate construction.

An epoxy acrylate resin (NEOPOL#8411 by Japan Upica Co., Ltd.) is used as a matrix material. Gelcoat contains milled CF reinforcements.

2. Core material

The core material must have flexibility to easily fit the contour of the mould, provide for air passages with any intervals required, withstand negative pressure and be heat-resistant. Endgrain balsa was chosen as a core material that will meet these requirements.

Table 1.

An example of CF hybrid laminate construction

ORDER	MATERIALS	REMARKS
1	Gelcoat	"TORAYCA" Powder 8% mixed
2	CF-Mat	"TORAYCA"#003B
3	CF-Cloth(UD Tape)	"TORAYCA"#1303 (Periphery)
4	CF-Cloth	"TORAYCA"#6644
5	GF-Mat	450g/Sq.m
6	GF-Woven Roving	600g/Sq.m
7	GF-Mat	450g/Sq.m
8	CF-Cloth	"TORAYCA"#6644
9	CF-Cloth(UD Tape)	"TORAYCA" #1303 (Periphery)
10	CF-Mat	"TORAYCA"#003B
11	Balsa Cores	Endgrain 15mmt
12	CF-Mat	"TORAYCA"#003B
13	GF-Woven Roving	600g/Sq.m
14	GF-Mat	450g/Sq.m
15	CF-Cloth	"TORAYCA"#6644

MATRIX : Epoxy Acrylate Resin

Figure 3 shows the details of a CF hybrid Mould Construction.

Figure 3. Details of CF hybrid mould section

A FORMING APPLICATION : SHOWER RECEPTOR PAN USED IN A COOLING TOWER HAVING A DIAMETER OF 2 METERS

The CF hybrid GRP mould by the new construction method was used in actual application. The remainder of this paper describes significant advantages of new method that were proven in this application. This refers to a formed shower receptor pan that fits to a metal plate cylinder of cooling tower. The pan is a semi-spherical product, 2 meters in diameter, made of ABS sheet which is 6mm thick. A high dimensional accuracy is required so it perfectly matches the metal cylinder of the tower.

Figure 4. shows a picture of the balsa cores layed up to the mould in process.

Figure 5. is a picture of back of the complete mould, showing a vacuum suction nozzle at the center.

Figure 6. shows the mould set in a moulding press, and a removed pan on the table in the front.

Figure 4. The balsa cores layed up to the mould in process

PROVEN ADVANTAGES OF THE CF HYBRID GRP MOULD

1. High heat-resistance to maintain rigidity of the surface skin in high temperature

The ABS sheet is pre-heated to approximately 200°C before forming. Moulding temperature is transferred to the part of the mould tool that contacts the sheet, and the mould itself is sometimes heated to 140°C.

Bending modulus of elasticity of the CF hybrid surface skin is approximately 1500kg/mm² at a normal temperature, and is reduced to about 250 kg/mm² at 140°C due to softening of matrix. (The bending modulus of elasticity of GRP alone is 120 kg/mm² at 140°C).

The balsa cores must be arranged at an appropriate interval to prevent the surface skin that has such a bending modulus elasticity from being pulled towards the air passages during vacuum suction, with the square patterns being left as warpage on the surface.

In the particular application being reported, the interval between two balsa core pieces was calculated to be 10mm maximum, and the amount of deflection of such a span is expected to be less than 0.0002mm which is perfectly negligible.

2. Dimensional accuracy of products

The periphery of this mould is constructed with a double lamination of a unidirectional CF cloth (TORAYCA#1601).

Thermal expansion of this mould is extremely minimized by such a laminate construction.

Table 2 shows coefficients of thermal expansion of different mould materials.

Table 2.

Thermal expansion coefficient of the mould materials

MATERIALS	EXPANSION COEFFICIENT ($10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$)	
	GENERAL VALUES	MEASURED VALUES*
G R P	8~22	18.0
Unidirectional CFRP	0.2	-
ALUMINUM	23.7	-
STEEL	12.3	-
TITANIUM	8.5	-
CF Hybrid GRP	-	3.2
Unidirectional CF Hybrid GRP	-	0.9

* Samples were picked up from the mould

Figure 5. The back of the complete mould, showing a vacuum suction nozzle at the center.

Figure 6. The mould set in a moulding press, and a removed pan on the table in the front.

A measured coefficient of thermal expansion of the unidirectional CF hybrid GRP used at the periphery of this mould is $0.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$.

Consequently, change in the diameter of this mould due to a change in the mould temperature from 20°C to 140°C is calculated to be 0.22mm which is negligible value.

An aluminum mould of similar size expands by 6mm, and a GRP mould expand by 4.5mm in a similar situation.

This accuracy maintaining capacity of the CF hybrid GRP mould being reported significantly reduces dimensional inaccuracy among products. This improved accuracy can further improve efficiency of cooling tower assembly, or save manhour, by more than 10%.

3. Reduce weight of moulding tool

A conventional aluminum mould weighs approximately 1500kg, and a GRP mould still weighs as much as 1200kg including resin concrete reinforcement.

A CF hybrid GRP mould weighs only 150kg approximately, resulting in 1/10 to 1/8 weight reduction.

This virtually corresponds to a reduction in manhour by over 30% in the mould setting.

4. Improved forming cycles

Input and output nozzles may be provided in the mould to send cold air along the air passages provided between the cores. This results in a shorter time needed to cool the mould surface, about half the time needed to cool the conventional moulds. This means an improved forming cycle, about two times the conventional cycles. This is attributed partly to CF which has a high thermal conductivity.

5. Economy

The production cost of this mould was approximately 30% of the aluminum moulds, and 80% of the GRP moulds. Delivery time was reduced to less than a half. No information is available at this stage as to the mould life, although the mould is expected to last almost endlessly since it is not subjected to any extreme stresses, provided that the mould is appropriately maintained periodically. This means a smaller redemption amount and term. Our records indicate a reduction of 25% in the cost in their total performance.

CONCLUSION

Although the working principle of the construction method was always regarded as highly effective, its implementation was somewhat hampered because of material availability and costs. Conventional metals or GRP could have been used to implement the idea. However, there were more problems than advantages. It would not have been put into use without CF hybrid GRP. CFRP alone could have been used to form the surface skin, but CF hybrid GRP was chosen as the more advantageous choice from the stand point of impact-resistance of the mould itself and economy.

We may add that use of CF hybrid GRP moulds for GRP moulding is steadily increasing in Japan.

Last, but never the least, we would like to express our sincere appreciation to Toray Industry Co., Ltd. for their assistance.

REFERENCES

Toray Ind. Co., Ltd. : "Carbon Fibre 1980" - 1981